

Balancing access and income – the dilemma of museum image licensing

By [Douglas McCarthy](#), published 14 July 2024.

[René-Charles Dassy and His Brother Jean-Baptiste-Claude-Amédée Dassy](#), 1850, by Hippolyte Jean Flandrin (French, 1809–1864). Cleveland Museum of Art, CC0

Analysing financial data from museums and trends in the image licensing industry, this post evaluates the current profitability and future viability of museum picture libraries. It also examines the opportunity cost to public access associated with the picture library model, considering museums' educational and societal goals.

Navigating a challenging financial climate

Under normal circumstances, museums contend with challenging financial conditions, including unstable funding streams, high operating costs, and limited resources. These difficulties were exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic, which caused a significant decline in tourism and visits to cultural venues. In 2020, Tate Modern, the British Museum, the National Gallery, and the Victoria and Albert Museum (V&A) saw an average 78% drop in attendance compared with 2019.¹ Unsurprisingly, self-generated income at these institutions fell precipitously.

Therefore, it is entirely reasonable for museums to seek income through various means, such as ticketing, merchandising, and image library sales. In my [previous article](#), I outlined how museums often use restrictive copyright and licensing policies to limit public access to their digitised collections. Museum picture libraries are built on this same legal foundation. So, how do they operate?

Anatomy of a museum picture library

Through online platforms, museum image libraries offer high-quality images of digitised collections for various uses. Users can search and browse these digital repositories, select images, and purchase licences based on the intended use, such as academic research, publications, or commercial products. Pricing is determined by factors like usage type and duration. Once purchased, users download the images under specific terms of use, with museum staff providing support and ensuring compliance with licensing agreements. The overall aim is to generate income while making the museum's collections accessible.

Profitability analysis and industry dynamics

How profitable are museum picture libraries, once running costs (such as staff salaries, software licensing, web hosting, and so on) have been accounted for? It's difficult to really know. Institutions rarely make this information available of their own volition. Museum's annual accounts are insufficiently granular. Furthermore, income-generating departments at museums (usually including the picture library) are sometimes sequestered in arms-length bodies that are immune from Freedom of Information requests.

Financial performance across four museums

To make a proper assessment of museum picture libraries' finances, we need a lot more data. But let's look at what we do know. In recent years many Freedom of Information requests² on this topic have been made to museums in the UK. The question is usually framed as follows:

“How much has your museum raised in revenue by selling images and/or licences for images, annually, after all costs have been accounted for?”

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<https://www.theartnewspaper.com/2021/03/30/british-museum-hit-hardest-by-2020-lockdown-among-uks-big-museum>

² <https://www.whatdotheyknow.com/>

Here is sample data from four museums that answered the above question. Note that 'Outcome' in the right-hand column of each table indicates whether the institution made a profit or loss from image licensing in the stated financial period. All figures are in pound sterling (£), the currency of the United Kingdom.

Government Art Collection

Financial period	Outcome
2013	No profit
2014	No profit
2015	No profit
2016	No profit
2017	£180

National Museums Liverpool

Financial period	Outcome
2018/9	-£7,471
2019/20	-£14,027
2020/21	-£19,070
2021/22	-£16,510
2022/23	-£14,795

Wallace Collection

Financial period	Outcome
2012/13	£9,000
2013/14	£8,000
2014/15	£10,000
2015/16	£6,000
2016/17	£9,000

National Gallery, London

Financial period	Outcome
2021/22	-£37,575
2022/23	£16,527
2023/24	-£47,615

Note: The National Gallery Picture Library pays an annual licence fee of £100,000 internally to the National Gallery in order to operate. This fee often obliterates the income generated by the Picture Library, resulting in the net losses seen above.

We cannot know how representative these numbers are of the wider sector, but they suggest that museums often struggle to profit much, if at all, from licensing images of their collections.

Impact of industry dynamics

It's important to realise that museum picture libraries are part of an image licensing industry which has undergone massive disruption in recent years. First, a wave of mergers and acquisitions absorbed many smaller businesses into a handful of global giants such as Getty Images, Shutterstock and Alamy. Then new models for buying and selling images emerged, including the following:

- **À la carte pricing:** Customers purchase individual images for specific uses.
- **Microstock:** Platforms sell images at very low prices, relying on high sales volume.
- **Free:** Images are made available for free use under generous licences. Examples include Pixabay, Pexels, Unsplash.
- **Open access user-generated content (UGC).** Examples include Flickr and Wikimedia Commons.
- **Open GLAM:** Cultural institutions provide free and open access to their collections.
- **Subscription:** Customers pay a regular fee to access libraries of free images.
- **Generative AI:** Emerging technologies that create images, videos and music based on user prompts.

These developments, combined with the explosive growth in the volume of available images online³, have significantly reduced the cost of buying images.⁴

Museum picture libraries are part of this landscape. Though they sometimes have unique items in their collections – cultural treasures no one else has – digital copies of those gems can usually be found online (however dubious their provenance). Broadly speaking, museum image

³ <https://photutorial.com/photos-statistics/>

⁴ Jim Pickerell (2021). Eleven Year Shutterstock Growth Trends – Stock Photography News, Analysis and Opinion, 2021. <https://www.selling-stock.com/Article/eleven-year-shutterstock-growth-trends>

libraries are just as vulnerable to market disruption and technological innovation as the many photographers⁵, stock image libraries and visual artists who now struggle to make a living⁶ from their assets.

Understanding value beyond financial metrics

Finances are crucial for museums, but fulfilling institutions' public missions goes beyond numbers on a spreadsheet. How many opportunities to create positive social, educational, and economic impacts are missed due to restrictive access policies to museum collections? How many potential users and contributors of cultural heritage are financially excluded by the current system?

While we may never have complete certainty, there is ample anecdotal evidence to consider. Take, for instance, a discussion on X last year about the acquisition of heritage images, where archaeologist Dr. Tess Machling's followers expressed their frustration:

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<https://brutallyhonestmicrostock.com/2024/01/30/why-selling-microstock-images-to-large-publications-pays-so-little-in-2024-five-examples-from-my-own-sales>

⁶ <https://fernandoamaral.org/ai-stock-photographer/>

"It insists its existing photos are not good enough for publication, and makes authors pay £££ for new photography, on top of licensing fees. Even when a perfectly fine, publishable photo exists. It's a shakedown."

"I don't see why, for reasons of cost, archaeology publications - particularly produced by cash-conscious institutions, small publishers and scholars - should be image-impooverished zones"

"We paid for an illustration ... It worked well in that instance and we were commissioning a few others but more annoying for the principle"

"I love the subject and get pleasure out of studying it, but I draw the line at paying to reproduce my own photos as that's purely for the benefit of others"

"Many projects I wanted to do involving national collections were stopped because curators were willing but wouldn't support publication because if costs"

"I know several curators who haven't published work because they need to pay"

"The person I was dealing with was sympathetic but felt their hands were tied by instructions they'd received"

"I didn't get a quote ... for a photo as my Editor and I know of problems with them on this front so we just went our own way"

"My undergrad dissertation was refused publication as I couldn't afford to pay image rights to convert them"

"We had to get publication funding from a local archaeological society. Seems wrong that a local society should be funding a national museum"

"Whoever was in charge ... didn't like him quite as much and said that he would be charged 50 GBP for each photo. He had to embargo all his photos for the online version of his thesis"

"Attempting to get copyright clearance for images was a major factor in me never publishing."

"Working on two projects, both of which I had planned on sourcing a few images from X. Clearly not happening now."

"Accessing their image collections is horrendous. Impossible to download images for non-profit use ... won't even let you screengrab or left click/save."

"I've written a number of books on ancient history for primary school age children ... I was unable to use any photos of items in X Museum and I also could not use photos I'd taken at X because the license was too expensive."

"I ended up having to hand draw every single inscription to save a huge amount of money. Massively time consuming."

"I'm actively choosing sources held in European collection at the moment, because they are either free or a minimal charge for administrative costs."

"My thesis images also ended up in the thousands of pounds so I didn't include them in the publication."

"Monograph based on my PhD was never published because X would not let me use photos I had taken ... It would have cost over £10k so their photographer could rephotograph them. Even now no one can see the objects in my online thesis catalogue"

"I had something similar for my book from Another Big Institution claiming I couldn't use my own photos from the venue"

"The X is forbidding the author from publishing pictures they themselves took in a PUBLIC museum in a scholarly work."

"Drawing or omissions were my experience or pulling whole article. It is a break on the thing that museums should want most, interpretation."

Tweet by Dr Tess Machling, 3 October 2023⁷

Note all of these comments related to just *one* national museum – this is the tip of the iceberg.

⁷ https://x.com/Tess_Machling/status/170916812224050290?s=20

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Conclusion

Considering the financial data we have now and observing industry trends, the outlook for museums monetising collections through image licensing appears bleak. Despite the unique value of some items, the presence of vast, low-cost, or free image repositories undermines the profitability of museum picture libraries. Museums must navigate this challenging landscape by exploring alternative revenue streams while remaining committed to making their collections accessible to the public. Embracing innovative approaches and collaborations may help museums strike a better balance between income generation and fulfilling their educational and cultural missions.

Museum leaders should carefully weigh the opportunity cost of restrictive access policies for digitised collections. If a picture library consistently loses money in pursuit of elusive profits while alienating its natural allies – researchers, historians, educators, and others – that represents a deeply unproductive approach. Digital collections are a key currency of modern audience engagement, but the typical current limitations on reuse mean that opportunities to create positive social, educational, and economic impacts are being missed.